

**ХАРЧОВА АЛЕРГІЯ ТА АТОПІЧНИЙ ДЕРМАТИТ ЯК ТРИГЕРНІ
ФАКТОРИ ТЯЖКОЇ ТА ТРИВАЛОЇ РОТАВІРУСНОЇ ДІАРЕЇ У ДІТЕЙ
РАНЬОГО ВІКУ**

**FOOD ALLERGY AND ATOPIC DERMATITIS AS TRIGGER
FACTORS OF SEVERE AND LONG-TERM ROTAVIRUS DIARRHEA IN
EARLY-AGED CHILDREN**

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Introduction. The pathogenesis of rotavirus diarrhea is based on the defeat of mature enterocytes of the small intestine by rotavirus with the development of carbohydrates malabsorption and activation of intestinal secretion. Allergic lesions of the intestinal mucosa are also accompanied by damage to enterocytes and even their destruction, and therefore may be an aggravating factor in the course of rotavirus gastroenteritis in children, which requires further study.

Objective. To evaluate the effect of concomitant food allergy (FA) and atopic dermatitis (AD) on the severity and duration of the diarrheal syndrome in rotavirus infection (RVI) in early-aged children.

Material and methods. The study group consisted of 60 children with proven RVI aged 1-24 months, who were treated in department number 4 of the Municipal Institution "Zaporizhzhya Regional Infectious Clinical Hospital" of the Zaporizhzhia Regional Council. The study group was divided into two subgroups depending on the presence of allergic pathology. The first subgroup included 20 children with FA and atopy. The second subgroup included 40 children without allergic pathology and a burdensome family history of allergies. A comparative assessment of the severity of diarrheal syndrome in the dynamics of the disease, its duration, and clinical manifestations of carbohydrate malabsorption (flatulence, intestinal colic) accompanying rotavirus diarrhea was conducted. Statistical processing of the results was performed using the software package "STATISTICA for Windows 13" (StatSoftInc., №JPZ804I382130ARCN10-J).

Results. There was a tendency to a higher daily incidence of diarrhea in children with FA and/or AD compared with patients without allergies from the 3rd

day of the disease - 4.00 [3.50; 7.00], against 3.00 [2.00; 5.00] times a day, respectively ($p > 0.05$). A significant difference was registered from the 5th to the 7th day, when patients with concomitant allergic pathology had liquid stools with a frequency of 4.00 [3.50; 7.00] and 4.00 [2.00; 5.50] times a day, respectively, which is 1.33 and 2 times higher than children without it ($p < 0.05$). At the beginning of the second week of the disease, the daily frequency of defecation in subgroups did not differ ($p > 0.05$), but the proportion of children with diarrhea on the 10th day of RVI was three times higher in the subgroup of patients with allergic pathology - 55% (11 children), against 17.5% (7 children) ($\chi^2 = 8.78$, $p < 0.05$). The duration of the diarrheal syndrome in children with FA and/or AD was 1.3 times higher than in patients without allergies - 10.00 [9.00; 12.00] days, against 7.50 [6.00; 9.00] days, respectively ($p < 0.05$).

Rotavirus diarrhea was accompanied by flatulence in 85% (17) of patients and it was accompanied by intestinal colic in 45% (9) in the presence of concomitant allergies, which is 1.6 times ($\chi^2 = 4.75$, $p < 0.05$) and 1.8 times ($\chi^2 = 4.10$, $p < 0.05$), respectively, exceeded the frequency of registration of these symptoms in children without allergies.

Conclusion. The presence of concomitant FA and/or AD in early-aged children with rotavirus gastroenteritis is a trigger for severe and prolonged diarrhea, which is more often accompanied by such manifestations of carbohydrate malabsorption syndrome as flatulence and intestinal colic.